

The growing role of English prepositions and postpositions in Stylistics Syntax

Həsənova Nüşabə

<https://orcid.org/0009-0005-2351-2548> , nushabehasanova89@gmail.com

Azerbaijan University of Languages, Translation Faculty, Azerbaijan

Abstract. Prepositions are characterized as one of the fundamental blocks in the formation of relations between linguistic units within a sentence. Therefore, we should not lose the sight of the fact that prepositions necessarily fall under the scope of Syntax which is directly investigates relations in the sentence. This article deals with the stylistic devices employed in Stylistics Syntax, with the focus on the usage of prepositions and their increasing importance in the formation of extra emotional meaning and coloring in creative literature. Over the course of language development, Linguistics blossomed out into another sub-branch called Stylistics which offers broader and novel perspectives on interpretations of texts on both literary and non-literary planes. Simultaneously, stylistics explored the concepts of meaning and form in its own way. Consequently, the correlation of central and contextual meanings from stylistics point of view stemmed from the interaction of thought and expression in larger linguistic units which stretches beyond the limits of separate sentences. Thus, if we look through the lens of Stylistics, we surely can claim that ideas were materialized in the form expressions, making them de-automatized. Form merges with aesthetics, specifically in belles-lettres style, where form gains additional meaningful features as well as information. During our investigation we used both descriptive method to define and classify the existing studies on the referred topic and by analyzing and interpreting instances from belles-lettres style we applied contextual analysis. As a result of our analysis, we come to the conclusion that hailed as empty or form words prepositions and postpositions were and are being used as the bearers of specific foregrounded meaning and authors use prepositions and postpositions and the functional shift between them as a way to convey the desired effects of repetition, force, persuasion, accentuation and so forth.

Key words. *Stylistics Syntax, Stylistic devices, prepositions, postposition, parallelism, chiasmus, repetition, lexico-syntactical SDs*

Introduction.

Nowadays, stylistic analysis of literary texts is gaining pace more than ever before. In stylistic analysis some rules of languages can be bent or stretched to the breaking point .[1,p 3] The significance and objective of stylistic analysis was argued as: *Stylistic analysis should pinpoint the physical elements in the text, underlining disembodied intention and imparting of feeling and emotion of the author.* [2, p2]

In ancient times, language of literature was considered as the highest register of intercourse. Stylistics is predominantly concerned with the specific usage of language and particularly with the purpose and artistic effect of the usages in question. All these features of Stylistics decidedly

were recycled of the ancient ideas persisting for a long time. In ancient rhetorics styles were classified as high style, middle and low style. High style was extensively used in poetics and low style in a more daily conversations.[2, p 1] Prepositions and postpositions alongside with conjunctions as the main indicators of relations within the sentence is extensively used to convey and showcase various stylistic devices both lexical and syntactical. The significance of prepositions has been overshadowed by numerous traditional views preventing it to get the credentials it truly deserves. Being aware of the significant presence of prepositions and postpositions in terms of expressing certain meaning and vehicles for achieving emotional effects will make stylistic analysis more comprehensive which underlines the objective of undertaken article.

According to conventional views in linguistics prepositions were interpreted and classified into various groups: In the first group linguists classify prepositions as belonging to lexico-grammatical groups where prepositions display both semantic and syntactic features (A.Smirnitski, B. İlyish, B.Aksenenko), in the second group prepositions were identified as formal – grammatical groups where only syntactical features of prepositions were observed (M.Steblyn-Kameski, A.Tsibina), in the last group prepositions were considered showcase generalized grammatical meaning and in the similar vein they were regarded as the direct equivalent and expressive means of nouns' case forms. [3, p 22]

Proceeding from the nature of Stylistics, we can savely claim that it shares both static and dynamic way of evolution. To illustrate, Stylistics never stays at the same place, always evolving and branching out within itself, on the other hand certain core ideas of stylistics are rearticulated form ancient rhetorics, maintaining its credibility. As from outer borders (cognitive stylistics, corpus stylistics, pragmatic stylistics), stylistics also branched out internally being classified corresponding to language levels. Stylistics Syntax prevailingly focuses on the organization of linguistic forms syntactically in English utterances. It deals not only with the purely outer arrangement of words but also establishes itself at the same time on more meaningful aspect of a speech, represented by emotionally colored words. Stylistics syntax is realized with the certain stylistic expressive means and stylistic devices which are considered as the foregrounding nature of a language.

Prepositions are abundantly employed in literary contexts, conveying and emphasizing certain relations. In stylistics alongside with lexical devices, syntactical stylistic devices are also exposed to versatile analyses by many researches. Notwithstanding the fact that syntactical stylistic devices are predominantly associated with pure structural composition of a sentence, structural arrangement of units within sentence also generates meaning, giving contextual meanings to linguistic units. Consequently, besides clearly distinguished lexical and syntactical SDs, another hybrid group incorporating both lexical and syntactical properties manifest itself in the classification of stylistic devices, namely lexico-syntactical devices. While lexical SDs are based on the opposition of lexical meanings regardless of syntactical structures of utterances, for syntactical SDs the opposite is true. With regard to lexico-syntactical devices, they are based on the opposition of lexical meanings with syntactical arrangement of words. It is not accidental that the boundaries between lexical and syntactical SDs are not rigid as we observe certain overlapping and melting properties into each-other. The following classification of Stylistic devices are observed in Stylistics.

Lexical SDs are – Metaphor, Metonymy, Irony, Polysemantic effect, Zeugma, Pun, Interjections, Epithet, Oxymoron, Antonomasia, Euphemism, Hyperbole, Proverbs and Sayings, Epigrams, Quotations, Allusions

Syntactical SDs are – Supra-phrasal units, Stylistic Inversion, Detached construction, Parallel construction, Chiasmus, Repetition, Enumeration, Suspense, Asyndeton, Polysyndeton, The gap-sentence link, Ellipsis, Break-in-the-narrative, Represented speech, Rhetorical question

Lexico-Syntactical SDs are: Antithesis, Climax, Anticlimax, Simile, Litotes, Periphrasis.

Materials and Methods

Descriptive and contextual analysis were used to identify the objective of the presented article.

In the course of contextual analysis of samples from creative literature, numerous usages with their interpretations were presented throughout the article.

Parallelism

In parallelism (parallel construction) the identical syntactical pattern reappears expressed by different words. As we mentioned before, no other SD device can exist in an isolated form. Therefore, many SDs are accompanied and backed with other SDs. Parallelism is mainly accompanied by repetition, polysyndeton or antithesis. In the following examples we can witness that repeated prepositions reveal the presence of parallelism which can disguise itself at certain cases.

We can observe instances where prepositions (the only lexical representation remaining unchanged) remain the same while other wordings change, leaving the same structure.

*We women love **with** our ears, just as men love **with** eyes.* [4,p 314]

*His beauty had been to him **but** a mask, his youth **but** a mockery* [4,p 342]

Parallelism + Repetition

In some cases first clause with no apparent parallelism is followed by parallel structures in the form of lengthy clauses and phrases. With respect to prepositions, in the following example it is clearly seen that prepositional noun phrase *the cry of* has been reoccurred along the pattern. During contextual and structural analysis of syntactical SDs we can decidedly put forward that the main emphasis and emotional power is fallen on the second part of the given structures.

There were two cries heard, the cry of a hare in pain, which is dreadful, the cry of a man in agony, which is worse [4,p 321] – here the writer by comparing two types cries clearly put emphasis on the second one, displaying its brutality.

*Whether the American and Yorkshiremen understand each-other, may **depend on** the intelligence of the 2 individuals concerned, upon their general experience with foreign dialects and languages, upon their disposition at the moment, upon the extent to which the situation clarifies the value of the speech utterance and so on.* [5, p 45]

It can be inferred from the presented instance that the use of **upon** stems from the phrase (depend on) and changes form from more daily usage (informal) to more formal usage. However, in the following structures postposition *on* is transformed into preposition *upon* by adding extra emotional stylistic color and stress to the phrase.

Chiasmus – Reversed Parallel Construction

In Chiasmus the subject and object of the sentence changes their places with more emotional focus on the desired effect. Here specifically the first part of the sentences pales in significance in comparison with the second part as the emotional emphasis is articulated in the second part of a sentence.

*Nothing can cure **the soul but the senses**, just as nothing can cure **the senses but the soul** [4, p 102]*

*Nowadays **all the married men live like bachelors**, and **all the bachelors like married man**. [4, p 293]*

In these examples writer used prepositions *but* and *like* effectively to display the stark contrast between the parts of the sentences.

Polysyndeton/Repetition

Polysyndeton is characterized by the overuse of connectives such as conjunctions and prepositions.

*One has a right to judge **of a man** by the effect he has over his friends. Yours seem to lose **of all sense, of honour, of goodness, of purity**. [4, p260]* - in former sentence of is used in the meaning of about a person, however in the latter example the qualities a man possess.

Antithesis

***The highest, as the lowest**, form of criticism is a mode of autobiography.[4,p 77]*

In a number of instances, writers use transformation of postpositions to prepositions by changing their conventional order, namely in the pattern of *verb+ postposition*, writer to make more emphatic effect on certain noun phrase changes the place of postposition putting it in front of noun phrase.

*He procured from Paris no less than nine large copies of the first edition, and had them bound in different colors, so that they might suit his various moods and the changing fancies of a nature **over** which he seemed, at times, to have almost entirely **lost control** [4,p 230]* – In order to create desirable effect in this example the postposition *over* (in the phrase lose control over sth) is placed before the verb before noun phrase, becoming syntactically preposition.

We can observe numerous samples when the author plays with the structure of phrasal verbs, underlining the importance of necessary parts within a sentence.

*In doing what I am going to do, what you force me to do, it is not **of your life** that I am **thinking**. [4, p285]*

It was **of himself**, and **of his own future** that he had to think [4, p 342]

I tell you Dorian that is **on things like these** that our lives depend.[4, p 338]

In some cases the referred transformation of postposition to preposition serves the function of the framing technique as the given phrase frame (encompass) all the sentence within itself by starting the sentence in the function of preposition and finishing it with the base phrase hence

forming an imaginary frame for the rest of the sentence. The major aim of this framing technique is to showcase the significance and add extra emotional coloring to the beginning of the sentence as in the following example.

Of the asceticism that deadens the senses, as of the vulgar profligacy that dulls them, it was **to know nothing** . [4, p 235]

Conclusion. As a result of the contextual analysis, we can claim that the utilization of prepositions not only shifts the readers' focus to the desired places intentionally crafted by the authors but also it forces readers' mind to find the logical links between the parts of the sentences.

Despite the fact that in conventional grammar and linguistics prepositions and postpositions are hailed as empty or function words, we can observe the versatile usages of them in literary texts to elucidate certain stylistic effects, including framing, logical emphasis and intensification of emotiveness.

Discussion.

With the novel development in the field of Stylistics Syntax and the emergence brand new sub-branches of Stylistics , functionalist stylistics, cognitive stylistics, corpus stylistics, pragmatic stylistics, just to name a few [6, p3] the need for deeper understanding of the role of prepositions and postpositions becomes necessary during stylistic analysis and stylistic pedagogy. While future studies conducted in Cognitive stylistics can direct focus on readers' level of perception of written text, Corpus linguistics can offer a myriad number of opportunities to reveal the frequent usage of prepositions and its reason with the assistance of computers.

Bibliography

1. Paul Simpson, Stylistic: A Resource book for students, Psychology Press, 2004, 247 pages
2. Burke, M. (Ed.). The Routledge Handbook of Stylistics, New York, 2015, 56 pages
3. Hajiyeve E. Functional-semantic features of auxiliary parts of speech in modern English and Azerbaijani languages, Baku, Muterjim, 2006, p 272
4. Wilde. O. The Picture of Dorian Gray, Selections , Volume one, Moscow Progress publisher, 1979
5. Bloomfield. L. Language , London, George Allen &Unwin LTD, 1933, p 553
6. Norgaad N., Busse B., Montoro R. Key terms in Stylistics , ISBN 978-0-8264-1288-1 (hardcover) ISBN 978-0-8264-1948-4 (pbk.), p 276 , 2010